

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381828230>

Quantum dots

Conference Paper · June 2024

CITATIONS
0

READS
3

1 author:

[Konstantinos Kotsis](#)
University College Dublin

175 PUBLICATIONS 1,125 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

In silico modelling of coated CdTe/CdS/ZnS quantum dots for nanosafety

Konstantinos Kotsis¹

¹ *School of Physics, University College Dublin, Ireland*

Quantum dots (QD) are nanocrystalline structures with unique, often size dependent, optical properties. QDs have been widely used as semiconductor materials in electronic devices or as photostable fluorescent labels for biomedical applications. However, before using QDs in patients for diagnostic imaging, a detailed study of the interactions in the human body, specifically as to whether they accumulate, if they are biodegradable, how they are eliminated as well as whether they induce long-term cytotoxicity, is necessary. QDs with a cadmium-containing core, a metallic shell and organic ligands for steric stabilisation were synthesized at BOKU/Austria [1, 2]. Measurements of the physicochemical properties and possible cytotoxic effects show that PEG-QDs indicate higher colloidal stability in the cell media after 24h than NAC-QDs. The cell viability was lower for PEG-QDs than for NAC-QDs. ROS production was significantly higher for PEG-QDs than for NAC-QDs and all QDs were internalized into the cells, at which CLSM images indicated the formation of QD aggregates.

To facilitate the interpretation regarding aggregation, corona formation, dissolution rates, and cytotoxicity of the coated QDs in silico modelling of the molecular dynamics is utilised. The structures of PEG-CdTe/CdS/ZnS, NAC-CdTe/CdS/ZnS and DHLA-PEGO750Me-CdTe/CdS/ZnS were modelled using a python tool. Electronic structure properties were calculated with quantum chemical methods and molecular properties with molecular dynamics methods. The descriptors served in the prediction of the reactivity and biological activity as well as stability and solubility of the coated QDs in cell media. Moreover, to identify the types of aggregation and to obtain dissolution rates of the coated QDs in water computations of molecular dynamics of large scale were needed and the data only partially support the experimental findings. Corona formation studies and predictions of cytotoxicity are in progress. This work was funded through EU Horizon 2020 Programme, grant n^o 731032 (NanoCommons), and SFI grant n^o 16/IA/4506.

[1] F. Part, C. Zaba, O. Bixner, T. A. Grünewald, H. Michor, S. Küpcü, M. Debreczeny, E. De Vito Francesco, A. Lassenberger, S. Schrittwieser, S. Hann, H. Lichtenegger, E.-K. Ehmoser, Doping Method Determines Para- or Superparamagnetic Properties of Photostable and Surface-Modifiable Quantum Dots for Multimodal Bioimaging, *Chemistry of Materials* **30** (2018) 4233-4241.

[2] C. Zaba, O. Bixner, F. Part, C. Zafiu, C. W. Tan, E. K. Sinner, Preparation of water-soluble, PEGylated, mixed-dispersant quantum dots, with a preserved photoluminescence quantum yield. *RSC Advances* **6** (2016) 27068-27076.